

Figure S10. Comparison of enriched ontology clusters of the top 150-ranked proteins upregulated 1 and 2 h after OFC between the OFC-positive and OFC-negative group
 We performed enrichment analysis using the top 150-ranked proteins upregulated 1 h (A) and 2 h (B) after OFC and selected the term with the lowest p-value within each cluster as the representative term in the dendrogram. The heatmap cells are colored according to their p-values, and grey cells indicate a lack of enrichment for that term in the corresponding gene list.